

Environmental Considerations in the Simulation of Early Earth Ultraviolet Conditions for Prebiotic Chemistry Experiments

Christopher Jacob Magnani¹

Received _____; accepted _____

¹Harvard College, Cambridge, MA 02138

Acknowledgements: Dimitar Sasselov, Ph.D., Sukrit Ranjan, Scot Martin, Ph.D., Marcelo Guzman, Ph.D., Adam Bateman, Ph.D.

ABSTRACT

This study examines the UV environments created in the laboratory in order to simulate prebiotic conditions and explore the chemistry of life’s origins. The majority of studies examining prebiotic chemistry do not provide details of the simulated ultraviolet environment beyond which UV lamp was used. By explicitly determining the ultraviolet spectra, we were able to compare experimental conditions with the spectra of both the modern Sun and a solar analog, κ -Ceti, representing the Sun during the era of biogenesis. Specifically, this paper examines the UV environments implemented in two experiments simulating prebiotic conditions: one examining ribonucleotide synthesis (Powner et al., 2009) and the other examining the viability of the reduction of oxaloacetate to malate, a step in the Reductive Tricarboxylic Acid (rTCA) Cycle (Guzman and Martin, 2008). These studies demonstrated that reactions could be driven forward through photoelectrochemical pathways, which in the case of the Powner experiment was wavelength dependent. While neither study detailed the ultraviolet environment used, Guzman and Martin noted some literature values, stating that UV fluxes on the Earth 3.5-3.9Ga ago should be 40Wm^{-2} for 315-400nm, 5Wm^{-2} for 280-315nm, and 1Wm^{-2} for 200-280nm (Guzman and Martin, 2008). For our study, we explicitly obtained the lamp spectra in order to determine the actual ultraviolet environments employed by these experiments. We were able to obtain spectra for a PenRay low-pressure Hg UV cold cathode lamp, an Ace Glass 450W medium-pressure mercury arc lamp with a quartz immersion well and water-cooling jacket, and a Newport 150W low-pressure Hg(Xe) lamp. Our results found that none of the lamps produced spectra that remotely resembled prebiotic conditions, as each failed to produce a continuum or replicate solar emission features. Furthermore, the flux ratios measured for the 150W and

450W lamps generally differed from those calculated from the literature values. Because the lamps inadequately simulate primordial conditions, better experimental designs are required to ensure realistic prebiotic chemical experiments. The accuracy of the simulation is important because several photochemical reactions involved in prebiotic synthesis are wavelength-dependent, and ultraviolet light has the ability to destroy bonds in key molecules, rendering a potential synthesis invalid (Calvert and Pitts, 1966).

1. Purpose

The purpose of this study is to review and examine prevalent methods used in prebiotic chemistry experiments to simulate prebiotic conditions in the laboratory. Particularly, we will compare the ultraviolet environment generated by arc lamps to an astrophysical understanding of the actual prebiotic environment, which is determined by using solar analogues to represent the Sun at primordial times (Ribas et al., 2010). An evaluation of laboratory methods is critical because much of prebiotic synthesis relies on wavelength-dependent photoelectrochemistry, and as such it will be useful to review laboratory results within a precise environmental context, allowing us to determine possible improvements to the simulation of prebiotic conditions.

2. Introduction

The quest to explain the origins of life hinges on an understanding of the environment present on the prebiotic Earth. The organic precursors of the first biological molecules were essential milestones on the path to the formation of the first cell, and it was the combination of the available chemical materials with environmental conditions that first

enabled their formation (Powner et al., 2009). As the conditions simulated are so crucial to the outcome, laboratory experiments hoping to recreate the processes that generated these molecules must attempt to accurately recreate prebiotic environmental conditions because significant variations will produce results that are not representative of primordial processes as they occurred on the early Earth. Before we examine attempts to move the prebiotic world into the laboratory, we must first examine several of the major environmental factors to be considered in the exploration of prebiotic chemistry.

2.1. Considerations for the Prebiotic Environment

Life originated on Earth over 3.5 Gyr ago, perhaps as early as 3.8 Gyr ago, which coincides with the final stages of the heavy bombardment of the inner solar system by asteroids and comets (Chyba and Sagan, 1992). In considering prebiotic chemistry, there are three key sources for organic molecules on the early Earth: extraterrestrial objects, impact shock driven synthesis, and organic synthesis on the Earth’s surface via energy sources such as UV radiation or electrical discharge (Chyba and Sagan, 1992).

During the bombardment, materials rich in organic molecules originating from comets, carbonaceous asteroids, and interplanetary dust particles made their way to the primordial Earth’s surface. Meteorites can serve as shields for the molecules in their core from the heat generated at impact, while small dust grains are often able to deliver their molecular payload nearly intact because they can be properly decelerated by the atmosphere (Chyba and Sagan, 1992). Furthermore, the quantity of material supplied by these two sources can be estimated using scaling models that utilize the lunar impact record (Chyba and Sagan, 1992).

Furthering the cause for the key role of extraterrestrial objects in delivering key

molecules to the prebiotic Earth is the presence of amino acids found in meteorites. It has also been demonstrated that analogues of icy interstellar dust grains can serve as sites for organic synthesis propelled by photolysis under ultraviolet conditions, as ice on the dust grains contains a variety of materials that are needed for organic synthesis, including amorphous H_2O , CO_2 , CO , CH_3OH , and NH_3 (Berstein, Dworkin, Sandford, Cooper, and Allamandola, 2002). In experiments replicating the ice grains and the interstellar environment, it was found that racemic mixtures, meaning 50-50 mixtures of enantiomers, of glycine, alanine, serine, glycerol, ethanoalamine, and glyceric acid could be produced in this manner, likely due to a pathway utilizing a variant of Strecker Synthesis harnessing radicals to transfer ultraviolet energy to the chemical reaction (Berstein et al., 2002). While racemic mixtures were produced by this experiment, exploration of extraterrestrial synthesis may provide an astrophysical mechanism explaining the enantiomeric excess of left-handed chiral molecules in modern biology, as well as those organic molecules found on meteorites (Berstein et al., 2002).

Additionally, the impacts of the extraterrestrial objects themselves would have been able to shock-synthesize organic materials in Earth's atmosphere. Shock synthesis of organic molecules can occur when meteorites travel through the Earth's atmosphere. These meteorites' shock waves then participate in organic synthesis by supplying heat to reducing gas mixtures in the prebiotic atmosphere, which contained ample CH_4 , N_2 , and H_2O (Chyba and Sagan, 1992). Laboratory experiments simulating heat exposure to these gas mixtures have demonstrated that a variety of hydrocarbons as well as amino acids can be produced through this process (Chyba and Sagan, 1992).

Of course, several sources of prebiotic organic materials are derived from the Earth itself. Simulated environments often vary in chemical composition depending on the location on the planet being examined, but regardless of location, prebiotic chemistry requires an

input of energy due to the decrease in entropy resulting from the synthesis of complex molecules. The field’s two most popularly employed sources of energy for propelling the reaction forward are electrical energy originating from lightning or ultraviolet radiation from the Sun (Chyba and Sagan, 1992).

2.2. The Prebiotic UV Environment

Ultraviolet radiation was much more abundant on the prebiotic Earth than today. The absence of oxygen in the primordial atmosphere resulted in the Earth’s surface being less shielded in the ultraviolet; furthermore, observations of young solar analogues suggest that the Sun had a larger ultraviolet luminosity at shorter wavelengths than it does today (Chyba and Sagan, 1992). Figure 1 depicts the ultraviolet energy levels received on the Earth’s surface between 4.4 and 3.6 Gyr ago, and it shows a clear increase in ultraviolet radiation received at earlier times (Chyba and Sagan, 1992). Figure 2 shows in black the ultraviolet spectrum of κ -Ceti, an analog of the young Sun, as compared to the ultraviolet spectrum of the present day Sun, given in red (Ribas, 2010). It is important to observe that both spectra show clear emission features, such as Lyman- α along with a continuum in the UV. While both spectra clearly demonstrate a trend with increased emission at longer wavelengths, the analog of the young Sun has greater emission at shorter wavelengths than the Sun does today (Ribas, 2010). In addition to the absorptive nature of oxygen present in today’s atmosphere discussed above, we must also consider the influence of water on the ultraviolet spectrum relevant to the prebiotic environment. Figure 3 shows that the presence of a layer of water has the effect of attenuating the ultraviolet spectrum of κ -Ceti, and with more water present, increased attenuation occurs (Ranjan and Sassellov, Private Communication, 2013).

Fig. 1.— **Ultraviolet Energy Received from the Sun:** We see above that in earlier times the Sun provided more energy in the ultraviolet, particularly at shorter wavelengths. The y-axis gives the ultraviolet energy received by the Earth, while the x-axis gives the time in the past in Gyr. These trends were obtained through observations of solar analogues.

UV Starlight: continuum & emission lines

Fig. 2.— **UV Spectrum of the Present Day Sun and κ -Ceti, a Solar Analogue:** We see above that the ultraviolet spectrum of the present day Sun (in red) and the solar analogue κ -Ceti (in black) both feature emission lines like Lyman- α as well as continuous emission at other wavelengths, with an increasing trend towards longer wavelengths. The solar analogue also exhibits higher emission than the present day Sun at shorter wavelengths.

Fig. 3.— **Effect of Water on the UV Spectrum of κ -Ceti:** The above spectrum shows the effect of a layer of water on the ultraviolet spectrum received from the solar analogue κ -Ceti at a distance of 1AU. The figure shows that water causes attenuation at short wavelengths, which becomes more pronounced when a greater quantity is present.

2.3. Exploring the prebiotic world in the lab

With an understanding of the environmental factors important to consider in a discussion of prebiotic chemistry, we now turn our attention to methods employed in the lab to simulate the primordial environment. Since the inception of prebiotic chemistry as a field in the 1950s, a great deal of progress has been made towards understanding the processes critical to biogenesis. It is therefore important to review the major advances in order to see what our efforts have achieved and how the prebiotic world is viewed from a laboratory perspective. Particularly, we will highlight the incorporation of prebiotic environmental considerations in experimental design.

Because a synthesis decreases entropy by building a more complex molecule from simpler constituent parts, it is necessary to supply an energy source to drive the reaction forward, and a successful experiment will result when the rate of the forward reaction

exceeds that of the reverse decomposition. The three major sources for this energy considered by prebiotic chemists are heat, electrical discharge, and ultraviolet radiation.

These energy sources generally limit the possible locations for prebiotic chemistry to occur, and the most accepted environments considered are concentrated solutions of organic compounds in pools on the Earth's surface as well as hydrothermal systems on the ocean floor. Generally the surface environment is favored as it allows for exposure to the atmosphere, lightning, and ultraviolet radiation (McCollom, 2013). Because the precise chemical environment on the prebiotic Earth is difficult to determine and depends on the location on the Earth's surface being simulated, there is a great deal of variation in experimental design. Consequently, prebiotic chemistry experiments generally focus on pieces of the puzzle, trying to demonstrate the viability of individual processes that can then be fit together within the greater synthetic framework. Furthermore, it is important to note that these experiments typically yield racemic mixtures of products. Because modern biology, as well as many molecules found on meteorites, exhibits an enantiomeric excess of left-handed chirality, there is a clear gap in any mechanistic understanding, as the reduction of this racemic mixture to a single preferred isomer remains unexplained (McCollom, 2013).

In the 1950s, the Miller-Urey Experiment showed that amino acids could be synthesized from a combination of materials thought to be present in the prebiotic atmosphere and ocean when an electric current was applied (Miller and Urey, 1959). They used two connected flasks to represent the atmosphere and the ocean, while sparks generated between electrodes provided the energetic source for the reaction. These spark-discharge experiments seek to simulate the effects of lightning, which they then harness to drive the synthesis forward. Their experiment was successful, producing a variety of amino acids as well as other important molecules including urea, HCN, carboxylic acids and amines (Miller and Urey, 1959).

While the conditions they used are today considered to be unrepresentative of the environment present at biogenesis, their great contribution was the linking of environmental factors to the synthesis of biological precursors, an essential step in initiating the quest to explain biogenesis. Particularly, they demonstrated that spark-discharge could propel variations of Strecker Synthesis, a reaction that produces an amino acid from an aldehyde (or ketone) by condensing it into an aminonitrile, which is then hydrolyzed into an amino acid. (Miller and Urey, 1959). Furthermore, their experiment demonstrated the possibility of using high-energy fluxes, be it from ultraviolet radiation or spark-discharge, to harness proper atmospheric conditions to produce aldehydes and HCN, which could then accumulate on the surface of bodies of water where further synthesis can occur (Miller and Urey, 1959). More recent predictions of the prebiotic atmosphere describe a relatively neutral atmosphere rich in N_2 and CO_2 with low concentrations of CH_4 and H_2 , as opposed to the reducing atmosphere consisting of CH_4 , NH_3 , and H_2 favored in the Miller-Urey Experiment (McCollom, 2013). While yields have been lower with these conditions, yields are still high enough to support atmospheric pathways as a potential source of the aldehydes and HCN needed for amino acid synthesis (McCollom, 2013).

Alternative chemical pathways have been tested attempting to replicate the environment in hydrothermal systems, hoping to harness thermal energy to drive reactions forward, and many of these have produced detectable amino acid concentrations (Yoshino, Hayatsu, and Anders, 1971). Effective mechanisms set in a hydrothermal environment utilize metal alloys or minerals as catalysts for a Fisher-Tropsch Synthesis, which can produce amino acids from gaseous CO , H_2 , and NH_3 bubbling out of the vent (Yoshino et al., 1971). Despite their results, many of the experiments required much higher concentrations of starting materials than present in modern hydrothermal vents to produce acceptable yields, making them vulnerable to criticism (McCollom, 2013).

While a good deal of work has been done on the prebiotic synthesis of amino acids, much progress has also been made on pathways explaining the origins of RNA. RNA consists of ribose sugar and nucleobases, and consequently there has been a good deal of emphasis placed on demonstrating viable pathways for the synthesis of these components. However, efforts to combine them have proved problematic, suggesting the possibility of a simpler precursor to RNA (McCollom, 2013). The synthesis of ribose has traditionally been accomplished with the formose reaction, as it necessitates only mild heating; however, the reaction is non-specific and produces a variety of sugars, of which ribose is often as little as 1% (Shapiro, 1988). Furthermore, the reaction requires concentrations of formaldehyde that are unlikely to have been present on the prebiotic Earth. To circumvent the issue, some experiments have implemented either boron or lead ions, which can increase yields of pentose sugars like ribose (Ricardo, Carrigan, Olcott, and Benner, 2004). Alternatively, the presence of glycoaldehyde phosphate selects for ribose 1,6-phosphate, but a mechanistic explanation for its prebiotic presence does not exist (McCollom, 2013).

A variety of experiments have also demonstrated possible syntheses of nucleobases, but they have inherent challenges. The 1961 Orò and Kimball experiment produced adenine under prebiotic conditions, but at yields of less than 1%, while other experiments have produced small amounts of guanine at yields 10 to 40 times lower than adenine (McCollom, 2013). Furthermore, the high concentrations of reactants required by these experiments have since rendered them incompatible with the prebiotic environment. Additionally, HCN, a crucial molecule in purine synthesis, is highly susceptible to hydrolysis under an alkaline pH; however, freezing the dilute HCN in the sample can circumvent this problem, as it enhances the effective concentration available for synthesis (Sanchez and Orgel, 1966). Regarding the other bases, spark-discharge experiments using mixtures of methane and nitrogen gas have produced cytosine, from which hydrolysis can be used to provide a pathway producing uracil (McCollom, 2013). Additionally, nucleobases are unlikely to have

favored accumulation on a broad scale because of their decomposition rates, suggesting that accumulation was limited to isolated pools on the Earth’s surface (McCollom, 2013).

It can be seen from this discussion that the single greatest challenge facing prebiotic chemistry experiments is the division between the laboratory and the actual conditions present on the prebiotic Earth. Consequently, it is essential that experiments be designed to accurately simulate the prebiotic environment.

3. Examination of Two Experimental Simulations of Prebiotic UV Environments

The remainder of this paper is devoted to an examination of the approaches that two groups used to simulate ultraviolet conditions in the lab. The first experiment we will examine was performed in 2009 by Powner, Gerland, and Sutherland to demonstrate a syntheses of ribonucleotides, and the second was performed in 2008 by Guzman and Martin to demonstrate the viability of a step of the rTCA cycle.

3.1. Powner, Gerland, and Sutherland’s Experiment

Forming RNA from its constituent parts has proved to be difficult, particularly due to challenges in the selective formation of ribose, its subsequent combination with nucleobases, various structural isomers, and the heavy thermodynamic preference for hydrolysis over bond formation. However, Powner, Gerland, and Sutherland proposed an elegant mechanism that provides a plausible route circumventing these issues. Instead of building up RNA from its constituent parts, they instead utilized an arabinose amino-oxazoline and an anhydronucleoside intermediate, which could then decompose into the desired derivative (Powner, Gerland, and Sutherland, 2009). By harnessing inorganic phosphate throughout

the reaction as their acid/base catalyst, nucleophilic catalyst, pH buffer, and chemical buffer in the synthetic steps prior to its incorporation into the end product (Powner et al., 2009), they were able to demonstrate a strong consistency in their simulated chemical environment at all stages of the synthesis, thereby adding tremendous credibility to their results.

Of particular interest, the final stage of their pathway, given in Figure 4, utilizes exposure of β -ribocytidine cyclophosphate to ultraviolet radiation, resulting in its decomposition into the desired uracil derivative, while simultaneously destroying most of the undesired co-products of the reaction (Powner et al., 2009). This is particularly important to note, as that photochemical reaction is wavelength dependent, requiring ultraviolet radiation at 254nm (Powner et al., 2009). Because of its wavelength dependence, the reaction in Figure 4 is reliant on a particular UV environment, and hence a proper modeling of prebiotic conditions is essential. To create an ultraviolet environment exhibiting the required radiation, they used a PenRay low-pressure Hg UV cold cathode lamp, tunable to the desired 254nm wavelength (Powner et al., 2009). We received the lamp's spectrum through a private communication with PenRay, and it is shown in Figure 12. The significance of their use of a lamp to generate this particular UV environment will be discussed later in this paper.

Fig. 4.— **A Wavelength Dependent Photochemical Step in the Synthesis of an Uracil Derivative:** The above figure shows the decomposition of β -ribocytidine cyclophosphate into an uracil derivative when exposed to ultraviolet radiation. The photochemical reaction is wavelength dependent, requiring 254nm UV radiation.

3.2. Marcello Guzman and Scot Martin's Experiment

In addition to Powner's, experiment we will also carefully examine a 2008 experiment performed by Marcelo Guzman and Scot Martin. Guzman and Martin demonstrated the viability under a prebiotic simulation of an enzymatically free conversion of oxaloacetate to malate, which is an important step in the Reductive Tricarboxylic Acid Cycle, or the rTCA cycle (Guzman and Martin, 2008). The rTCA cycle is given in Figure 5 with the oxaloacetate to malate conversion step highlighted in red, while Figure 6 provides the details of the oxaloacetate to malate conversion. The rTCA cycle is the reverse of the Krebs Cycle, converting CO_2 to citrate, and it has been identified as a possible source of molecules that could have supplied energy to precursor biological processes as well as fed the first cells prior to the evolution of photosynthesis or complex enzymes (Guzman and Martin, 2008).

The experiment relies on taking advantage of the reaction's thermodynamics to

demonstrate its viability. Photoelectrochemistry drives the forward reaction, resulting in both a dependence on the quantum efficiency of the semiconducting colloidal ZnS and an independence from temperature. ZnS was present in the primordial ocean, and it can serve as a semiconducting material able to capture ultraviolet energy through the excitation of an electron, which can then be used to reduce oxaloacetate to malate (Guzman and Martin, 2008). The reverse reaction is a temperature-dependent decarboxylation reaction, which converts oxaloacetate into pyruvate by releasing a carboxylic acid group as CO₂. Additionally, the reverse reaction follows an Arrhenius behavior and experiences slower kinetics at lower temperatures (Guzman and Martin, 2008). Consequently, the experiment optimized the reaction in the forward direction by maintaining the relatively low temperature of 280K (Guzman and Martin, 2008).

In their experiment, Guzman and Martin modeled an N₂ dominant prebiotic atmosphere with 0.1-10 atm CO₂, with oxygen purged from the system. For their photochemical apparatus, they used a 500mL glass reaction vessel outfitted with a waterjacket in a Neslab RTE-111 casing, which enabled temperature to be maintained between 278 and 323K. An Ace Glass 450W medium-pressure mercury arc-lamp equipped with a quartz immersion well was submersed in the reaction vessel (Guzman and Martin, 2008), and a replica of this apparatus is shown in Figure 10 with the isolated 450W lamp shown in Figure 9. The authors did not provide details regarding on the ultraviolet environment simulated, simply stating that light was generated between 200 and 400nm. While not stating the specifics of the experimental ultraviolet conditions, the authors did note some literature values for ultraviolet fluxes representing prebiotic conditions, which do not appear to have been directly used in the design of their experiment. They stated that the following are representative of prebiotic conditions on the early Earth: 40Wm⁻² for UVA (315-400nm), 5Wm⁻² for UVB (280-315nm), and 1Wm⁻² for UVC (200-280nm).

Fig. 5.— **The Reductive Tricarboxylic Acid Cycle:** The above figure gives shows the Reductive Tricarboxylic Acid Cycle (rTCA cycle), which is the reverse of the Krebs Cycle. Boxed in red is the oxaloacetate to malate conversion step that is the focus of Marcelo Guzman and Scot Martin’s 2008 experiment.

Fig. 6.— **Conversion of Oxaloacetate to Malate with Excitation of Colloidal ZnS:** The above figure shows the reaction that converts pyruvate to oxaloacetate and then oxaloacetate to malate, which are steps of the rTCA cycle. Also shown is the excitation of colloidal ZnS, which provides the excited electron needed for the reduction of oxaloacetate to malate.

4. Methods

In order to properly examine the relevance of the methods used to replicate prebiotic conditions, we needed to obtain ultraviolet spectra representing the experimental environments implemented in Guzman and Martin’s as well as Powner’s studies. With these spectra, we then were able to make comparisons with the spectrum of the solar analog depicted in Figure 2. We were also able to acquire spectra from a Newport 150W Hg(Xe) arc lamp. Because the Newport set-up is a fairly popular option in university chemistry labs, its spectrum is relevant for making comparisons. We must note that the pressure of the 150W lamp was not clearly labelled, but the lab tech assisting us in using the equipment believed it to be a low-pressure lamp. In the rest of this section we detail both how arc lamps work as well as the methods we used to acquire the spectra.

4.1. Ultraviolet Lamps

It is important to understand how the lamps used in this study work in order to appreciate the consequence of their use and interpret the major features present in their spectra. In this experiment, we took spectra from two types of arc lamps: an Ace Glass 450W medium-pressure mercury arc lamp equipped with a quartz immersion well and water-cooling jacket and a Newport 150W low-pressure Hg(Xe) lamp. Through a private communication with UVP PenRay, we were supplied a spectrum of the PenRay low-pressure Hg UV cold cathode lamp tuned to 254nm as used by Powner’s group, which is provided in Figure 12.

An arc lamp is designed with two electrodes separated from one another within a chamber filled with a specific kind of gas. The chamber walls are made of fused quartz in order to allow for better UV transmission as well as a better resistance to the lamp’s

temperature than offered by normal glasses (Anderson, 2004). As lamps age, the quartz envelope can mineralize, making it less transparent and decreasing the amount of UV emitted by the lamp (Anderson, 2004). When voltage is applied, an electric arc forms between the electrodes, which has the effect of exciting the gas in the chamber. These excited electrons then emit photons as they drop energy levels (Anderson, 2004). Due to pressure broadening, the lamps are supposed to emit at a range of wavelengths, not just the atomic emission lines of the gas, and according to the manufacturers, at least 28% of energy should be emitted in the UV (Anderson, 2004). In this study, the 450W lamp contained ionized mercury gas in its chamber while the 150W lamp contained a mixture of mercury and xenon.

Ultraviolet lamps used in chemical experiments typically belong to either of two different designs. Lamps are either placed outside the reaction chamber, providing external radiation, or placed within the reaction chamber via an immersion well. In this study both types of lamps were used for comparison purposes. The 150W lamp irradiates the reaction vessel externally, which provides the advantage of enabling a choice of filter. Figure 7 shows the 150W lamp used in our study with the lamp's casing and the reaction vessel clearly visible, while Figure 8 depicts the lamp itself, suspended within its casing. In contrast, the 450W lamp is immersed in the reaction vessel, which has the benefit of more direct radiation and enhanced environmental control with less interference from the surrounding oxygen in the air. Figure 9 depicts the 450W lamp without the immersion well. Both the immersion well and the lamp can be seen in the experimental set-ups given in Figures 10 and 11. Both lamps were equipped with power sources that had predetermined settings designed to maintain a voltage at 135V.

4.2. Experimental Procedure for the 150W Lamp

For the 150W set-up, the spectrometer, an OceanOptics USB2000, was placed on the mount for the reaction vessel seen in Figure 7. The spectrometer was then connected to a computer running OceanView software, and a background was taken before the lamp was turned on, which allowed the device to automatically perform a background subtraction from subsequent frames. The device also automatically stores reference and dark measurements which it uses to automatically correct the produced frames. The voltage source was turned on, supplying 135V to the lamp, and after a warm-up period of approximately 5 minutes, 50 frames were taken without any filters. We then decided to take spectra using either a low-pass or a high-pass filter in order to determine if they would be useful tools in adjusting the spectrum to better represent prebiotic conditions. The lamp was turned off and equipped with a low-pass filter before another 50 frames were taken with the spectrometer. This process was repeated again using the high-pass filter. Unfortunately the filters were not labeled, but they were found in a Thorlabs box, so it is presumed that Thorlabs was the manufacturer. After collection for the 150W lamp was complete, the data was transferred to Microsoft Excel, with which the 50 frames taken for each trail were averaged, and these averages were plotted to create each spectrum. The plots seen in Figures 13, 15, and 16 give the counts collected at each wavelength for the no filter, low-pass filter, and high-pass filter cases, respectively. Figure 14 provides a zoomed in version of the no filter case, providing just the ultraviolet spectrum.

Fig. 7.— **150W Lamp Experimental Set-Up:** Above is the experimental set-up for the Newport 150W Hg(Xe) arc lamp. Shown is the ultraviolet lamp casing, the mount for a filter, and the mount for reaction vessel. When taking the spectra, the spectrometer was placed on the reaction vessel mount. Note that the lamp is external to the reaction vessel.

Fig. 8.— **150W Lamp Inside the Lamp Casing:** Above we see the Newport 150W Hg(Xe) arc lamp housed inside its casing. The cylindrical piece to the right of the lamp is where the radiation leaves the casing, and this is pointed towards the reaction vessel.

4.3. Experimental Procedure for the 450W Lamp

For the 450W Lamp, we sought to exactly replicate the apparatus used in Marcelo Guzman and Scot Martin’s 2008 experiment, and we were able to use the same lamp that belonged to Guzman. The first experimental set up we implemented is depicted in Figure 10. The 450W lamp was placed inside the immersion well with tubes attached to allow for the flow of water through the water jacket. The immersion well was then placed within a 500mL reaction vessel that was suspended within the reaction safety cabinet. The spectrometer was held just outside the reaction vessel, as indicated in Figure 10, and a background frame was taken before the lamp was turned on and after the door of the safety cabinet was closed. The voltage source was then plugged in, supplying 135V to the lamp. Once 50 frames were collected, the device was promptly shut off, as it began to smoke. Understanding that the lamp was relatively old, we tried to minimize the time that it was actually on for safety reasons and to avoid an explosion. The data was transferred to Microsoft Excel with which the counts detected at each wavelength were averaged to produce the plot shown in Figure 17. Because large atomic emission lines dominate the spectrum, we zoomed in to create Figure 18 to provide better clarity. We also made Figure 19 to focus on the ultraviolet part of the spectrum.

After seeing the spectra, we noticed that there was no emission at the lower wavelengths, and determined that this may be due in part to the glass composing the reaction vessel. Consequently, we decided to repeat the experiment with the immersion well outside of the reaction vessel, and this set-up is shown in Figure 11. This second set-up removes much of the material between the spectrometer and the lamp, making it easier to get a good spectrum. Furthermore, this set-up more accurately represents the environment perceived by the reaction, as the reaction vessel is not between the reactants and the lamp. We then followed the same procedure described above to collect 50 frames, and we used

Microsoft Excel to average the frames and produce the plot shown in Figure 20. Just as above, atomic emission lines feature prominently, so we zoomed in to produce Figure 21 to provide for greater clarity. Figure 22 gives just the ultraviolet part of the spectrum.

Fig. 9.— **The Ace Glass 450W Medium-Pressure Mercury Arc Lamp:** The picture above shows the Ace Glass 450W medium-pressure mercury arc lamp that we used. This is actually the same lamp that belonged to Marcelo Guzman. When the lamp is used, it is inserted into an immersion well that is not present in the image.

Fig. 10.— **Experimental Set-Up 1 with the 450W Lamp:** Above is the first experimental set-up that we used, which recreates the apparatus used in Guzman and Martin’s 2008 experiment. The Ace Glass 450W medium-pressure mercury arc lamp is inside the immersion well, which itself is inserted into the reaction vessel. The spectrometer was held just outside of the reaction vessel.

Fig. 11.— **Experimental Set-Up 2 with the 450W Lamp:** Above is the second experimental set-up that we used, which recreates the apparatus used in Guzman and Martin’s 2008 experiment, except the immersion well is held outside of the reaction vessel. This was done to avoid the interference caused by the glass reaction vessel. The Ace Glass 450W medium-pressure mercury arc lamp is inside the immersion well, and the spectrometer was held just outside the immersion well.

5. Data and Analysis

5.1. Spectra

Here we provide the spectra taken using the procedures outlined above as well as the spectra of the PenRay low-pressure Hg UV cold cathode lamp used by Powner’s group, which we received through a private communication with PenRay.

Fig. 12.— **PenRay Low-Pressure Hg UV Cold Cathode Lamp Tuned to 254nm:** The above spectrum shows the ultraviolet environment created by the PenRay low-pressure Hg UV cold cathode lamp used by Powner et al. in their 2009 experiment synthesizing ribonucleotides. The y-axis gives the relative intensity, while the x-axis gives wavelength in nm. The peak emission is clearly visible at 254nm. We must note that this spectrum was provided by PenRay through a private communication, and consequently carries less weight in our discussion than those spectra that we explicitly measured ourselves.

Fig. 13.— **Spectrum of Newport 150W Lamp Without a Filter:** Above we see the spectrum obtained from the Newport 150W Hg(Xe) Lamp with intensity given in counts and wavelength in nm. We can see continuous emission from the ultraviolet to the infrared, with a good deal of thermal and visible emission due to the electrical arc between the cathode and anode in the lamp. Most atomic emission features are smoothed out from pressure broadening.

Fig. 14.— **Ultraviolet Spectrum of Newport 150W Lamp Without a Filter:** Above we see the ultraviolet part of the spectrum obtained from the Newport 150W Hg(Xe) Lamp with intensity given in counts and wavelength in nm. We can see that emission is continuous and increases with wavelength. Most atomic emission features are absent or smoothed out from pressure broadening.

Fig. 15.— **Spectrum of Newport 150W Lamp Equipped With a Low-Pass Filter:** Above we see the spectrum obtained from the Newport 150W Hg(Xe) Lamp equipped with a low-pass filter. We can see continuous emission in the ultraviolet, and the rest of the spectrum is cut off at around 378nm. Most atomic emission features are absent or smoothed out from pressure broadening.

Fig. 16.— **Spectrum of Newport 150W Lamp Equipped With a High-Pass Filter:** Above we see the spectrum obtained from the Newport 150W Hg(Xe) Lamp with intensity given in counts and wavelength in nm. We can see that the spectrum is cut off below around 600nm. The thermal and visible emission is due primarily to the electrical arc between the cathode and anode.

Fig. 17.— **Spectrum of 450W Lamp Using Experimental Set Up 1:** Above we see the spectrum collected from the Ace Glass 450W medium-pressure mercury arc lamp using the experimental set-up 1 depicted in Figure 10. The intensity is given in counts while the wavelength is provided in nm. Clearly visible are the mercury atomic emission features, and there is little activity at low wavelengths. The atomic emission features are so pronounced that it is hard to see anything else, therefore please refer to Figures 18 and 19, which are zoomed in for more clarity.

Fig. 18.— **Spectrum of 450W Lamp Using Experimental Set-Up 1, Zoomed In:** Above we see the spectrum collected from the Ace Glass 450W medium-pressure mercury arc lamp using the experimental set-up 1 depicted in Figure 10. The intensity is given in counts while the wavelength is provided in nm. Here we have a zoomed in version of Figure 17. Clearly visible are the mercury atomic emission features, and there is little activity at low wavelengths. However, we see continuous emission in the visible and infrared, between around 478nm and 878nm. This is due to the electrical arc in the lamp between the cathode and anode. This feature was hard to see in Figure 17, but here it is identifiable.

Fig. 19.— **Ultraviolet Spectrum of 450W Lamp Using Experimental Set-Up 1:** Above we see the spectrum collected from the Ace Glass 450W medium-pressure mercury arc lamp using the experimental set-up 1 depicted in Figure 10. The intensity is given in counts while the wavelength is given in nm. Here we have zoomed in on the ultraviolet part of the spectrum. We see some mercury atomic emission features, but there is little activity at low wavelengths due to absorption by the glass reaction vessel.

Fig. 20.— **Spectrum of 450W Lamp Using Experimental Set Up 2:** Above we see the spectrum collected from the Ace Glass 450W medium-pressure mercury arc lamp using the experimental set-up 2 depicted in Figure 11. The intensity is given in counts while the wavelength is provided in nm. Clearly visible are the mercury atomic emission features, and there is more activity at low wavelengths than we saw in Figures 17, 18, and 19. Again, the atomic emission features are so pronounced that it is hard to see anything else, therefore please refer to Figures 21 and 22, which are zoomed in for more clarity.

Fig. 21.— **Spectrum of 450W Lamp Using Experimental Set-Up 2, Zoomed In:** Above we see the spectrum collected from the Ace Glass 450W medium-pressure mercury arc lamp using the experimental set-up 2 depicted in Figure 11. The intensity is given in counts while the wavelength is given in nm. Here we have a zoomed in version of Figure 20. Clearly visible are the mercury atomic emission features, and there is more activity at low wavelengths than we saw with experimental set-up 1. We also see continuous emission in the visible and infrared, between around 478nm and 878nm. This is due to the electrical arc in the lamp between the cathode and anode. This feature was hard to see in Figure 20, but here it is identifiable.

Fig. 22.— **Ultraviolet Spectrum of 450W Lamp Using Experimental Set-Up 2:** Above we see the spectrum collected from the Ace Glass 450W medium-pressure mercury arc lamp using the experimental set-up 2 depicted in Figure 11. The intensity is given in counts while the wavelength is provided in nm. Here we have zoomed in on the ultraviolet part of the spectrum. We see some mercury atomic emission features, but there is little pressure broadening and an absence of continuous emission. The emission features at the lower wavelengths are now observed because the glass reaction vessel is no longer present.

5.2. Calculating the Flux Ratios

In Guzman and Martin’s study, they did not detail the specifics of the ultraviolet environment that they used in their experiment. They did, however, provide the following literature values representing prebiotic ultraviolet fluxes: 40 Wm^{-2} for UVA (315-400nm), 5 Wm^{-2} for UVB (280-315nm), and 1 Wm^{-2} for UVC (200-280nm). We then calculated flux ratios using these reported literature values to be 8 for UVA/UVB, 40 for UVA/UVC, and 5 for UVB/UVC. We were able to calculate ratios from our spectral data by first multiplying the counts at a given wavelength by the photon energy, $E=h\nu$, and then integrating over the given wavelength intervals. These values are given in Table 1 below. By dividing the resulting values appropriately, we obtained the desired ratios, which are given in Table 2.

	UVA	UVB	UVC
Wavelengths (nm)	315-400	280-315	200-280
	W^*m^{-2}	W^*m^{-2}	W^*m^{-2}
Literature Values	40	5	1
Device	J	J	J
150W Lamp (no filters)	6.133E-14	1.000E-14	5.161E-15
450W Lamp (set-up 1)	6.462E-16	8.867E-17	0
450W Lamp (set-up 2)	7.530E-16	5.941E-16	1.536E-15

Fig. 23.— **Table 1: Integrated Values for UVA, UVB, and UVC**

Above, we see the integrated values for the UVA (315-400nm), UVB (280-315nm), and UVC (200-280nm) bands. In each case, the integration was done using the emission features above the baseline. These values were then used to compute the flux ratios given in Table 2. Note that experimental set-up 1 with the 450W lamp did not have any features above baseline for the UVC region and the value for UVB is larger for experimental set-up 2 than observed in experimental set-up 1. Also provided are the fluxes in Wm^{-2} that Guzman and Martin cite from the literature (Guzman and Martin, 2008).

With these values we were then able to find the flux ratios of our spectra and compare these to the literature values. This information is given in Table 2 below:

	UVA / UVB	UVA / UVC	UVB / UVC
Flux Ratio (Literature)	8	40	5
150W Lamp (no filter)	6.13	11.88	1.94
450W Lamp (set-up 1)	7.29	n/a	n/a
450W Lamp (set-up 2)	1.27	0.49	0.39

Fig. 24.— **Table 2: Flux Ratios for the 150W and 450W Lamps as Compared to the Literature**

Above, we have used the integrated values from Table 1 to compute flux ratios between the UVA, UVB, and UVC bands. We also include flux ratios computed using the literature values provided by Guzman and Martin (Guzman and Martin, 2008). We see that the experimental set-ups do not entirely reflect the actual prebiotic conditions presented by the literature. While the UVA/UVB ratios for the 150W lamp and the 450W lamp using experimental set-up 1 are close to the literature value of 8, there is a clear difference in the UVA/UVC and UVB/UVC values in all cases. Also note that experimental set-up 1 for the 450W Lamp did not have any features above baseline for the UVC region, which resulted in the UVA/UVC and UVB/UVC ratios being undefined. Furthermore, experimental set-up 2 had a larger UVB value, resulting in the UVA/UVB value being lower for set-up 2 than observed in set-up 1.

6. Discussion

We see from the spectra that the laboratory experiments are generally not simulating prebiotic ultraviolet conditions, and the only values coming close to the literature are the UVA/UVB ratios observed in the 150W lamp and the 450W lamp with experimental set-up 1. Figure 2 gives the ultraviolet spectra of both the present-day Sun and a solar analog representing the Sun at the time of biogenesis. Both the Sun and solar analog feature continuous emission that increases with wavelength as well as some emission features, primarily Lyman- α . However, not one of the experimental spectra fits this pattern. We will focus our discussion on the ultraviolet sections of the spectra as they are most relevant with regards to the photoelectrochemistry essential to prebiotic synthesis.

The spectrum of the PenRay apparatus used by Powner, given in Figure 12, exhibits emission features with a peak at 254nm and lacks the continuum seen in the solar spectrum given in Figure 2. The PenRay apparatus produced results in the Powner experiment because it delivered the specific wavelength required by the wavelength-dependent photochemistry involved in this reaction; however, actual prebiotic conditions consisted of ultraviolet radiation at other wavelengths that is absent from this experimental design. Ultraviolet radiation has the ability to break bonds, and the other wavelengths present in prebiotic conditions could have inhibited the results presented in their study by disrupting earlier stages in the synthesis. We must note that because this spectrum was provided by PenRay through a private communication, it carries less weight in our discussion than the spectra taken from the other lamps that we explicitly measured ourselves.

Of the lamps examined in our study, the 150W lamp's spectrum is the closest to resembling the solar spectrum; however, there are still clear inadequacies. Firstly, the emission features present in the solar spectrum in Figure 2, such as Lyman- α , are absent in the ultraviolet spectrum of the 150W lamp given in Figure 14. Additionally, there is little to

no ultraviolet radiation below 228nm in the 150W lamp spectrum, unlike the solar spectrum in Figure 2. We can see in Table 2 that while the UVA/UVB ratio is close to the literature value of 8, the other ratios for the 150W lamp differ from the literature, as the values 16.63 and 2.25 for UVA/UVC and UVB/UVC, respectively, are much lower than the literature values of 40 and 5. This is due to the 150W lamp having more ultraviolet radiation in the UVC band, resulting in a more gradual decline in ultraviolet energy at shorter wavelengths than the solar analog’s spectrum given in Figure 2. Furthermore, we see that filters cannot be used to improve the spectrum to make it more like the prebiotic Sun, as the filters can do nothing more than cut out parts of the spectrum, as seen in figures 15 and 16.

We also find that the spectra taken from the 450W lamp do not adequately represent prebiotic conditions. Firstly, neither of the experimental set-ups produced a continuous spectrum as seen in the solar spectrum shown in Figure 2. We see that the spectra from experimental set-up 1 shown in Figures 17, 18, and 19 are dominated by the mercury emission features with the continuum effectively absent in the ultraviolet, as seen in Figure 18. We also see that the presence of the glass reaction vessel decreased ultraviolet radiation detected by the spectrometer below 300nm, as when the glass was removed in experimental set-up 2 more emission features are observed at shorter wavelengths, as seen in Figures 20, 21, and 22. However, these emission features are only those corresponding to the mercury in the lamp, and they do not reflect the solar features seen in Figure 2. Furthermore, as in the case of experimental set-up 1, we do not see a continuum in the ultraviolet. Finally, the flux ratios in Table 2 differ significantly from the literature values, primarily due to the absence of an ultraviolet continuum. While experimental set-up 1 exhibits a UVA/UVB ratio of 7.29 that is close to the literature value of 8, we see from the more complete spectrum obtained from experimental set-up 2 that there is actually more emission in UVB, resulting in the UVA/UVB ratio for experimental set-up 2 to be the much lower value of 1.27. The absence of both a continuum and solar emission

features in either experimental set-up, combined with the differences between their flux ratios and the literature, demonstrates the inadequacy of the 450W arc lamp in simulating prebiotic conditions. The Guzman and Martin experiment was successful only because the oxaloacetate to malate conversion merely required an excited electron, which was not wavelength-dependent; consequently, the mercury emission features in the ultraviolet were sufficient to drive this specific reaction. However, by not simulating prebiotic conditions accurately, it is unknown if ultraviolet features present in the actual prebiotic conditions and absent from the simulation would inhibit the results; furthermore, without an accurate simulation, we cannot be sure of environmental consistency when this reaction is fit into the larger prebiotic chemical framework leading to biogenesis.

7. Conclusions

Our results clearly shows that lamps are an unrealistic approximation of the prebiotic ultraviolet environment. It is essential to replicate prebiotic conditions accurately in these experiments, because only by doing so can we be certain that the reactions were indeed possible on the primordial Earth. Furthermore, by using accurately simulated conditions, it becomes possible to fit studies examining specific reactions into a larger framework explaining the generation of the biological precursors necessary for the genesis of life. Lamps may be easy to use, but they do not provide a precise simulation of the prebiotic world. Consequently, better methods must be used to provide a decent simulation of the prebiotic world. One possible solution would be to use a combination of sources, including tunable UV lasers and lamps, to provide both the continuum and the desired emission features, thereby better replicating the ultraviolet environment received on the primordial Earth's surface. Regardless of the experimental apparatus employed, the results of studies exploring prebiotic chemistry are only as relevant as the environmental simulation is accurate.

8. References

- Anderson, William T, Jr., (2004). The Quartz Mercury Arc. Ace Glass Incorporated. Retrieved from <http://www.aceglass.com>
- Bernstein, M. P., Dworkin, J. P., Sandford, S. A., Cooper, G. W., & Allamandola, L. J. (2002). Racemic amino acids from the ultraviolet photolysis of interstellar ice analogues. *Nature*, 416(6879), 4013. doi:10.1038/416401a
- Calvert, J.G. & Pitts, J.N. (1966). *Photochemistry*. New York: John Wiley & Sons. Print.
- Chyba, C. F. & Sagan, C. (1992). Endogenous production, exogenous delivery and impact-shock synthesis of organic molecules: an inventory for the origins of life. *Nature*, 355, 125132.
- Guzman, Marcelo I., & Martin, Scot T. (2008). Oxaloacetate-to-malate conversion by mineral photoelectrochemistry: Implications for the viability of reductive tricarboxylic acid cycle in prebiotic chemistry. *International Journal of Astrobiology*, 7(3&4), 271-278. doi: 10.1017/S1473550408004291
- McCollom, T. M. (2013). Miller-Urey and Beyond: What have we learned about prebiotic organic synthesis reactions in the past 60 years? *Annual Review of Earth and Planetary Sciences*, 41(1), 207229. doi:10.1146/annurev-earth-040610-133457
- Miller, S.L. & Urey, H.C. (1959). Organic compound synthesis on the primitive Earth. *Science*, 130(3370), 245-251. doi:10.1126/science.130.3370.245
- Powner, M. W., Gerland, B., & Sutherland, J. D. (2009). Synthesis of activated pyrimidine ribonucleotides in prebiotically plausible conditions. *Nature*, 459(7244), 23942. doi:10.1038/nature08013

Ranjan, S. (2013). Private Communication.

Ribas, I., Porto De Mello, G. F., Ferreira, L. D., Hebrard, E., Selsis, F., Catalan, S., Garces, A., Do Nascimento, J.D., & De Medeiros, J.R. (2010). Evolution of the solar activity over time and effects on planetary atmospheres. II. κ Ceti, an analogue of the sun when life arose on Earth. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 714, 384-395. doi:10.1088/0004-637X/714/1/384

Ricardo, A., Carrigan, M.A., Olcott, A.N., & Benner, S.A. (2004). Borate minerals stabilize ribose. *Science*, 303(5655), 196. doi:10.1126/science.1092464

Sanchez, R., Ferris, J. & Orgel, L.E. (1966). Conditions for purine synthesis: Did prebiotic synthesis occur at low temperatures? *Science*, 153, 72-73. doi:10.1126/science.153.3731.72

Shapiro, R. (1988). Prebiotic ribose synthesis: a critical analysis. *Origins of Life and Evolution of the Biosphere*, 18(3731), 71-85. doi:10.1007/BF02422027

UVP PenRay. (2013). Private Communication.

Yoshino, D., Hayatsu, K., & Anders. (1971). Origin of organic matter in early solar system-III. Amino acids: catalytic synthesis. *Geochemica et Cosmochimica Acta*, 35(9), 927-938. doi:10.1016/0016-7037(71)90006-8